

ASSESSING THE UNLAWFUL ENTERING ON PREMISES BILL, 2022: CONFLICTS WITH CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS AND THE PIE ACT PROTECTIONS

Abstract

This article examines the constitutionality of the *Unlawful Entering on Premises Bill, 2022* (hereafter the *Unlawful Entry Bill*). The primary purpose of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, if enacted into law, would be to repeal and replace the *Trespass Act 6 of 1959* (hereafter the *Trespass Act*) and to prohibit unlawful entry into premises. The *Trespass Act* has been identified as a piece of colonial and apartheid-era legislation originally intended to combat trespassing, publications, and conduct provoking hostility between certain population groups, and which has lost its relevance in South Africa's constitutional democracy. However, the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, paradoxically, contains similar provisions that undermine the constitutional imperatives and values of South Africa's constitutional democracy, and if enacted in its current form, would have adverse consequences for the majority black population.

The authors analyse the historical background of South Africa's forced removals and dispossession of land from black people by the white settlers through violence, deceit and racially discriminatory laws, which have resulted in today's unequal society. They go on to explore the prototypes of South Africa's trespassing laws to draw similarities with the *Unlawful Entry Bill* and its shortcomings in light of the *Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996* (hereafter the *Constitution*) and the *Prevention of Illegal Evictions from and Unlawful Occupation of Land Act 19 of 1998* (hereafter the *PIE Act*). The authors argue that the *Unlawful Entry Bill* contradicts the protections afforded by the *PIE Act* and various constitutional provisions, as it seeks to criminalise unlawful occupation and authorise evictions without judicial oversight.

Accordingly, the article concludes that the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, in its current form, fails to meet the prevailing constitutional standards and should be comprehensively redrafted to align with the *PIE Act*, the Constitution's transformative mandate, and the protection of vulnerable persons.

Keywords

Constitution; Evictions; Trespassing; Unlawful Occupation; PIE Act; PISA; Trespass Act; Unlawful Entering on Premises Bill

ASSESSING THE UNLAWFUL ENTERING ON PREMISES BILL, 2022: CONFLICTS WITH CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS AND THE PIE ACT PROTECTIONS

NK Sithole*
NS Siphuma**

1 Introduction

On 12 August 2022, the Department of Justice and Constitutional Development passed the *Unlawful Entering on Premises Bill, 2022* (hereafter the *Unlawful Entry Bill*).¹ The primary purpose of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, if enacted into law, would be to repeal and replace the *Trespass Act*,² (hereafter the *Trespass Act*) and to prohibit unlawful entry into premises.³ The Government Notice to the *Unlawful Entry Bill* indicates that the *Trespass Act* has lost its relevance in South Africa's constitutional democracy, as it has been identified as a piece of colonial and apartheid-era legislation originally intended to combat trespassing, publications, and conduct provoking hostility between certain population groups.⁴ This is a proverbial case of "the pot calling the kettle black" as the *Unlawful Entry Bill* appears to be similar to, if not more restrictive than, the *Trespass Act*.

The *Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996* (hereafter the *Constitution*),⁵ is the fundamental and authoritative source of the aspirational values of the South African legal system,⁶ and any law or conduct inconsistent with it is invalid.⁷ The *Prevention of Illegal Evictions*

* Nkosinathi Knowledge Sithole. LLB (Wits University). LLM in Property Law, *Cum Laude* (University of South Africa). Practising Attorney and Director of Litigation at the Socio-Economic Rights Institute of South Africa (SERI).

** Dr. Adv Nzumbululo Silas Siphuma. LLB (North-West University). LLM in Property Law, *Cum Laude*. LLD in Property Law (Stellenbosch University). Senior Lecturer: Department of Jurisprudence at College of Law, University of South Africa. Advocate of the High Court of South Africa. Editor-in-Chief: South African Mercantile Law Journal.

¹ Gen Not 46705 in GG 1219 of 12 August 2022.

² *Trespass Act* 6 of 1959.

³ Item 2 in Gen Not 46705 in GG 1219 of 12 August 2022 and section 11 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

⁴ Item 3 in Gen Not 46705 in GG 1219 of 12 August 2022.

⁵ The *Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996*.

⁶ Du Plessis 2005 SALJ 608.

⁷ Section 2 of the *Constitution*.

from and Unlawful Occupation of Land Act,⁸ (hereafter the *PIE Act*) was enacted to give effect to section 26(3) of the *Constitution*.⁹ The *PIE Act* abolished the previous system under which unlawful occupation of land constituted a criminal offence and prohibited evictions that result in homelessness. Ironically, resisting an eviction – lawful or unlawful - from one’s home for fear of being rendered homeless, may still result in arrest, prosecution and incarceration for contravening the *Trespass Act*. The *Unlawful Entry Bill* contains similar provisions and consequences which, if enacted in its current form, would undermine the constitutional imperatives and values of South Africa’s constitutional democracy.¹⁰

In his parliamentary budget speech for the 2021/2022 financial year, the then Minister of Justice and Correctional Services, Minister Lamola, observed that some pieces of legislation, while not overtly unconstitutional, unjust or anti-democratic, nonetheless formed part of a suite of legislative enactments designed to foster the policies of apartheid and have survived into the democratic era. He went on to say that:

The continued existence of these laws in our statute book is not compatible with our Constitutional order. We will lead the process to review and repeal these statutes. At the same time, great care should be taken to ensure that the abrogation of these statutes does not leave or create a lacuna in the law.¹¹

The *Trespass Act* is one of the examples of legislation designed to foster apartheid policies that Minister Lamola spoke about. Although the *Unlawful Entry Bill* - which seeks to repeal and replace the *Trespass Act* - has not yet been passed into law, this article aims to critique the *Unlawful Entry Bill* for being in direct conflict with the spirit, purport and object of the Bill of Rights in the *Constitution*.

To place this into perspective, this article is structured into three main sections before the conclusion. Part two of the article investigates the historical background of South Africa’s forced removals and dispossession

⁸ *Prevention of Illegal Evictions from and Unlawful Occupation of Land Act* 19 of 1998.
⁹ *Machele and Others v Mailula and Others* 2010 (2) SA 257 (CC) para 13 (hereafter the *Machele* case).

¹⁰ The preamble of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* states that it aims to prohibit unlawful entry on premises, and to provide for matters connected therewith. Its provisions, among other things, include the offence of unlawful entry and the penalties to be imposed if a person is found to be guilty of the offence (two (2) years imprisonment, or a fine, or both); the duty to inform an intruder (unlawful occupier) of unlawful entry; the powers of the police and defences to the unlawful entry.

¹¹ Department of Justice and Constitutional Development https://www.justice.gov.za/m_statements/2022/20220816-UnlawfulEntry-Bill.html.

of land from black people by the white settlers through violence and deceit, which resulted in today's unequal society. Part three goes on to explore the prototypes of South Africa's trespassing laws to draw the similarities with the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, while in part four, the article goes in depth to analyse the shortcomings of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* in light of the *Constitution* and the *PIE Act*. Finally, part five, in conclusion, provides the reason why the passing of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* would be diametrically in conflict with the spirit, purport and object of the Bill of Rights in the *Constitution*.

2 Historical background

Unlawful occupation of land in South Africa is not a contemporary phenomenon that occurs in a vacuum. Rather, it is a manifestation of centuries of colonisation, predominantly characterised by the dispossession of land from black people by the white settlers through violence and deception. This historical injustice was later formalised on 31 May 1910 with the establishment of the Union of South Africa, which introduced general racial restrictions on the acquisition of land by black people.¹²

The first of these racially designed segregation laws was the *Native Land Act*,¹³ (hereafter the *Native Land Act*), which was enacted to prevent black people from owning land beyond the designated areas within the so-called "native reserves".¹⁴ These comprised, at most, thirteen per cent of South Africa's land mass and forced black people to live in densely populated townships on the outskirts of urban centres.¹⁵ The *Native Land Act* sanctioned the initial systematic and gruesome dispossession of land from black people through the dismantling of their communal land rights and the confiscation of their livestock and property. The effect was the disintegration of an independent African agrarian society, which led to widespread poverty and displacement among black people and created a pool of cheap labour for an industrialising South Africa.¹⁶

¹² Muller *The Impact of Section 26 of the Constitution on the Eviction of Squatters in South African Law* 36. See also *Department of Land Affairs v Goedgelegen Tropical Fruits (Pty) Ltd* 2007 (6) SA 199 (CC) (Hereafter the *Goedgelegen case*) para 58.

¹³ *Native Land Act* 27 of 1913 (hereafter the *Native Land Act*).

¹⁴ These were some of the rural areas that were set aside as labour reserves for the whites and were commonly referred to as the Bantustans.

¹⁵ Kloppers and Pienaar 2014 *PELJ* 680. See also *Goedgelegen case* para 58.

¹⁶ Walker and Cousins *Land Divided, Land Restored* 24. See also *Government of the Republic of South Africa and Others v Grootboom and Others* 2001 (1) SA 46 (CC) para 6 (hereafter the *Grootboom case*).

The majority black population that found itself in unlawful occupation of land or property within South Africa was dealt with through the enactment of the *Prevention of Illegal Squatting Act* (hereafter the PISA).¹⁷ The PISA, together with the Trespass Act, formed the backbone of the apartheid state's arbitrary and summary eviction of those found to be in unlawful occupation. These enactments allowed the state to summarily demolish informal settlements which had spread across South African urban areas as a result of urbanisation.¹⁸

PISA was also aimed at eroding the remnants of the common law protection afforded to unlawful occupiers, which required that they not be evicted without a court order.¹⁹ A further objective was to eliminate any uncertainties that hindered rapid eviction.²⁰ The *Trespass Act*, introduced in 1959, sought to address those uncertainties, with the result that anyone who intentionally and unlawfully entered or remained upon land, building, or structure of another committed the offence of trespass.²¹

The intensification of apartheid's draconian legislation resulted in the widespread destruction and removal of long-established settlements in urban areas. Residents of areas such as Sophiatown and Newclare in Johannesburg, District Six in Cape Town, and Cato Manor in Durban were forcibly relocated to racially and ethnically segregated townships like Soweto in Johannesburg, KwaMashu and Umlazi in Durban, and Nyanga and Gugulethu in Cape Town - all situated on the peripheries of urban areas.²²

For the majority of unemployed black people from these old settlements, their fates were sealed with mass deportations and forced displacement to

¹⁷ *Prevention of Illegal Squatting Act* 52 of 1951.

¹⁸ Harrison 1992 *African Insight* 16. See also Strauss 2019 *Fundamina* 157-158.

¹⁹ Wilson, Dugard and Clark 2015 *SAJHR* 475.

²⁰ Muller *The Impact of Section 26 of the Constitution on the Eviction of Squatters in South African Law* 54-56, explains the purpose and provisions of the PISA as follows: Firstly, that it enabled a court to order the eviction of squatters and authorised the demolition of any buildings/structures that were erected on the land without the permission of the owner/lawful occupier. Secondly, that it prohibited the collection of fees or the exercising of authority with regard to the organisation of illegal squatting. Thirdly, that it afforded administrative powers to magistrates and native commissioners to effect the removal of squatters. Fourthly, that it afforded local authorities the power to establish emergency camps; and Finally, that it criminalised any obstruction of police and other authorised officials that were 'acting under the authority of an instruction or order issued' by a court.

²¹ Section 1 of the *Trespass Act*.

²² Harrison 1992 *African Insight* 16. See also Nieftagodien *The Soweto Uprising* 13-15.

ethnically demarcated Bantustans.²³ These mass deportations, however, did not halt urbanisation, as South Africa continued to industrialise to the exclusion of the Bantustans, where the majority of black people were confined amid widespread poverty.²⁴ The apartheid state's slow pace and eventual stagnant housing rollout led to the proliferation of a new generation of informal settlements and unlawful land occupation across South Africa.²⁵

The racially discriminatory system of apartheid officially came to an end in 1994, following the country's democratic elections. Democratic South Africa, comprising nine unified provinces, was initially governed under the Interim Constitution, which served as a transitional framework and guided the drafting of the Final Constitution, completed in 1996.²⁶ Many of the draconian racial segregation laws, including the *Native Land Act*, were repealed as early as 1991 through the enactment of the *Abolition of Racially Based Land Measures Act*.²⁷ This legislation was aimed at repealing apartheid laws that had imposed racial restrictions on land ownership and use.²⁸

3 The prototypes of the Unlawful Entry Bill

PISA, despite being part of apartheid-era laws that imposed racial restrictions on land ownership and use, remained in force after 1994 and was ultimately repealed by the enactment of the *PIE Act*, which gives effect to section 26(3) of the *Constitution*.²⁹ Section 26(3) of the *Constitution* provides that no one may be evicted from their home or have their home demolished without a court order. The PISA's companion legislation, the *Trespass Act*, remained in force and continues to be used as an instrument to facilitate swift evictions.³⁰

The main provisions of the Trespass Act are as follows:

Section 1(1) of the Trespass Act provides that: [A]ny person who, without the permission –

²³ Nieftagodien *The Soweto Uprising* 9-10 and 15.

²⁴ Harrison 1992 *African Insight* 17.

²⁵ Harrison 1992 *African Insight* 17-18.

²⁶ Dugard "International Law and the South African Constitution" 1997 *EJIL* 78.

²⁷ *Abolition of Racially Based Land Measures Act* 108 of 1991.

²⁸ Kloppers and Pienaar 2014 *PELJ* 687.

²⁹ *Machele* case para 13.

³⁰ Muller *The Impact of Section 26 of the Constitution on the Eviction of Squatters in South African Law* 70.

- (a) of the lawful occupier of any land or any building or part of a building; or
- (b) of the owner or person in charge of any land or any building or part of a building that is not lawfully occupied by any person, enters or is upon such land or enters or is in such building or part of a building, shall be guilty of an offence unless he has a lawful reason to enter or be upon such land or enter or be in such building or part of a building.

Section 1(2) of the *Trespass Act* provides that, for the purposes of subsection (1), the expression “lawful occupier” in relation to a building or part of a building does not include a servant of the lawful occupier of the land on which that building is situated.

On 11 May 1983, the *Criminal Law Amendment Act*,³¹ was passed to amend section 2 of the *Trespass Act* by substituting the original penalty of twenty-five pounds with two thousand rands and replacing the original term of imprisonment of three months with a term of two years, or both such fine and imprisonment.³²

On 28 November 1997, the *Extension of Security of Tenure Act* (hereafter ESTA),³³ came into operation. The effect of ESTA is threefold. Firstly, it amended the *Trespass Act* by inserting subsection (1A) under section 29, which provides that a person who is entitled to be on land in terms of ESTA shall be deemed to have lawful reason to enter and remain upon such land.³⁴ Secondly, ESTA amended the *Trespass Act* by inserting subsection (2) under section 29, which states that a court convicting any person under subsection (1) may make an order for the summary ejection of that person from the land concerned, provided that an occupier who has a right of residence or a right to use the land in terms of ESTA shall not be ejected from land in respect of which he or she has such a right.³⁵ Lastly, ESTA amended the *Trespass Act* by inserting section 3A, which states that this Act shall apply throughout the Republic.³⁶

³¹ *Criminal Law Amendment Act* 59 of 1983.

³² Section 1 of the *Criminal Law Amendment Act* 59 of 1983. In its original form, section 2 of the *Trespass Act* provided that:
“any person convicted of an offence under section *one* shall be liable to a fine not exceeding twenty-five pounds or to imprisonment for a period not exceeding three months”.

³³ *Extension of Security of Tenure Act* 62 of 1997.

³⁴ Section 29(1) of ESTA.

³⁵ Section 29(1) of ESTA.

³⁶ Section 29(1) of ESTA.

Having considered the legislative development and amendments to the *Trespass Act*, it is necessary to briefly outline the substantive elements that constitute the offence of trespass. The elements of the crime of trespassing are:

- (a) The conduct of entering or being upon the land or building or part of the building;
- (b) the unlawfulness of such conduct, which includes the absence of consent and a lawful reason for your conduct; and
- (c) intention.³⁷

An accused charged with committing trespass under the *Trespass Act* is not left without protection. To escape liability under the Act, the accused must justify their actions on one or more of the following grounds:³⁸

- (a) consent;
- (b) lawful reason; or
- (c) necessity.³⁹

In essence, section 1(1) of the *Trespass Act* creates two types of crimes: entering a property and being upon it without permission - either because permission has been withdrawn or was never granted in the first place. Under the circumstances, a domestic worker or caretaker of the building is not a lawful occupier in terms of the *Trespass Act*, and thus, anyone who enters or is upon the premises on that employee's permission is still guilty of contravening section 1(1).

In the case of unlawful occupiers protected by the *PIE Act*, their conduct involves more than merely entering or being upon the land; rather, their occupation is often in pursuit of a home that provides shelter and a place of abode.⁴⁰ The element of permanency can be inferred from their conduct in accessing the property as a home. In eviction cases, occupation usually depends on several factors, including the occupiers' intention, the history of their occupation, and their relationship with the property owner.⁴¹ Such conduct does not amount to criminality warranting sanction; rather, these issues arise from years of landlessness and the pursuit of security of tenure, which should be addressed by balancing rights in sections 25 and 26 of the Constitution.

³⁷ Snyman *Criminal Law* 556-557.

³⁸ These grounds are discussed in detail under heading 4.5 of this article.

³⁹ Snyman, *Criminal Law* 557-559.

⁴⁰ *Ndlovu v Ngcobo; Bekker and Another v Jika* 2003 (1) SA 113 (SCA) para 20 (hereafter *Ndlovu and Bekker* case).

⁴¹ *City of Johannesburg v Changing Tides 74 (Pty) Ltd and Others* 2012 (6) SA 294 (SCA) para 15 (hereafter *Changing Tides* case).

At the height of apartheid, the effects of the *Trespass Act* were particularly significant for reasonably settled black workers – particularly farm workers,⁴² garden workers,⁴³ domestic workers,⁴⁴ and, more generally, those who remained in urban areas or left the Bantustans to seek work in the cities. However, the application of the *Trespass Act* today does not distinguish between or enquire into a person’s background or class, the reason for trespassing, or their life circumstances.

Courts have cautioned against the impropriety of resolving civil disputes through a criminal prosecution,⁴⁵ and granting evictions of settled occupiers, particularly where such actions may result in homelessness.⁴⁶ Eviction is, by its nature, a matter of civil law. Accordingly, any attempt to secure the removal of unlawful occupiers through the *Trespass Act* should be strongly discouraged, especially given that the enactment of *PIE Act* was intended to mitigate the harsh effects of PISA, which are similarly reflected in the *Trespass Act*.

4 An analysis of the shortcomings of the Unlawful Entry Bill

4.1 Introduction

The *Unlawful Entry Bill* was introduced to repeal and replace the *Trespass Act*, should it be signed into law.⁴⁷ However, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* appears to be similar, if not worse than, the *Trespass Act*. As discussed in the sections that follow, the *Unlawful Entry Bill’s* application extends to unlawful occupiers who are otherwise protected under the *PIE Act*,⁴⁸ and effectively re-criminalises unlawful entry onto premises for purposes of human settlement, notwithstanding that section 26 of the *Constitution* and the *PIE Act* have decriminalised the unlawful occupation of a home.⁴⁹ Furthermore, as shown in the sections below, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* seems to have the potential to violate several rights protected in the *Constitution*. Alarming, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* grants the South African Police Service the powers

⁴² *R v Mgwali* 1961 (1) SA 51 (E).

⁴³ *R v Mgwali* 1961 (1) SA 51 (E).

⁴⁴ *R v Maduma* 1959 (4) SA 204 (N).

⁴⁵ *S v Ziki* 1965 (4) SA 14 (E).

⁴⁶ *Port Elizabeth Municipality v Various Occupiers* 2005 (1) SA 217 (CC) para 28 (hereafter *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case).

⁴⁷ Section 11 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

⁴⁸ Section 2 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

⁴⁹ Sections 3 and 10 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

to summarily evict unlawful occupiers from their homes and to arrest them if they fail to vacate - a chilling phenomenon that ought to have been buried with Apartheid.⁵⁰

4.2 Evaluating the Unlawful Entry Bill against section 26 of the Constitution and the PIE Act

Considering the provisions and history of the *Trespass Act*, the Government Notice's description and perception of the *Trespass Act* are not unfounded. The irony, however, lies in the intention to replace the *Trespass Act* with yet another trespass (or unlawful entry) law that is likely to provoke hostility between certain population groups in South Africa. When one considers the democratic government's faltering land reform programme and the slow progress in realising the right of access to housing under section 26(1) of the *Constitution*, the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, if enacted, will have far-reaching consequences for the majority of black South Africans.

The stated purpose of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* is to repeal the *Trespass Act*, prohibit unlawful entry onto premises, and provide for related matters. Amongst other things, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* establishes the offence of unlawful entry and the penalties applicable if a person is found guilty; the duty to inform an "intruder" of unlawful entry; the powers of the police; and defences available against the offence of unlawful entry.⁵¹

Some concerning provisions of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* include the following: Section 1, which provides definitions of key terminology used in the *Unlawful Entry Bill*. On examination, it is evident that most of these terms are merely breakdowns and expansions of the undefined words that appear in section 1 of the *Trespass Act*. This alone effectively makes the *Unlawful Entry Bill* a democratic-dispensation version of the *Trespass Act*, with the word "trespass" replaced by "unlawful entry on premises." Regrettably, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* introduces the term "intruder," defined as "a person who unlawfully enters on a premises or part of a premises." Such a phrase is open to misinterpretation and is likely to be wrongly used synonymously with "unlawful occupier," who is otherwise protected by the *PIE Act*. Moreover, commenting generally on a similar characterisation of occupiers as "invaders," the Constitutional Court condemned this type of labelling, noting that:

⁵⁰ Section 8 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

⁵¹ Item 4 in Gen Not 46705 in GG 1219 of 12 August 2022.

this description of human beings is less than satisfactory and cannot pass without comment. It detracts from the humanity of the occupiers, is emotive and judgmental, and comes close to criminalising the occupiers. This form of citation should not be resorted to. A more neutral appellation like ‘occupiers’ might well be more appropriate.⁵²

Section 2, which deals with the application of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* and lists exclusions, much like the *Trespass Act*, is intended to apply throughout the Republic, including in instances where the *PIE Act* also applies. The *Unlawful Entry Bill*’s failure to exclude the *PIE Act* from its application creates a legal oversight which could be exploited by opportunistic litigants seeking to unlawfully evict occupiers who are otherwise protected under the *PIE Act*. A clear distinction must be drawn between an unlawful occupier, whose rights are guaranteed by section 26(3) of the Constitution and the *PIE Act*, and an “intruder” as defined in the *Unlawful Entry Bill*. This overlap creates legal uncertainty and, in extreme cases, could facilitate the abuse of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* by diverting the government’s limited resources for policing crime in South Africa towards evicting, arresting, and detaining unlawful occupiers – echoing practices reminiscent of the apartheid era.

Section 3, which deals with the prohibited unlawful entry onto premises and provides for two offences similar to those in the *Trespass Act*: *entering the premises* and *the failure to leave or re-entering the premises*. Section 3(1) provides that a person who unlawfully enters premises commits the offence of unlawful entry, while subsection (3) provides that a person who has been directed, either orally or in writing, by a lawful occupier or any other authorised person to leave the premises and –

- (a) does not leave the premises as soon as practically after receiving the direction; or
- (b) re-enters the premises, is guilty of the offence.

The only defence to these charges, as provided in section 3(4) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, is that the person charged reasonably believed that they had title to, or an interest in the premises, that entitled them to enter.

The *Unlawful Entry Bill* criminalises individuals in circumstances that are similar to, and even beyond, those covered by the *Trespass Act*. The definition of unlawful entry includes cases where a person’s consent to enter has been withdrawn. During apartheid, it was possible to prosecute someone under these circumstances. However, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* not

⁵² *Occupiers of Skurweplaas 353 JR v PPC Aggregate Quarries (Pty) Ltd and Others* 2012 (4) BCLR 382 (CC) para 3.

only criminalises the occupation of premises when consent has been withdrawn, but it also extends criminal liability to situations where the occupier would otherwise have had consent. This creates the potential for individuals who are ordinarily entitled to be in a place to be prosecuted. For example, a new property owner could use the *Unlawful Entry Bill* against existing tenants of a recently purchased property, circumventing the *huur gaat voor koop* principle to evict tenants whose leases have not expired. Similarly, those who remain on workplace premises after working hours for other purposes or those who embark on a strike for better working conditions or salary increase demands could also be targeted under the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

Section 4, deals with limited permission to enter premises. It provides that -

- (1) Where notice is given that one or more particular activities are permitted, entry on a premises for those activities is permitted and entry on a premises for any other activity is prohibited.
- (2) Where entry on a premises is not prohibited under section 3 or by notice that one or more particular activities are permitted under subsection (1), and notice is given that a particular activity is prohibited, that activity and entry for that purpose is prohibited and all other activities and entry for that purposes are not prohibited.

The contents of this provision are confusing, excessively broad, and impractical to enforce. In a school setting, for example, as is often observed in higher education institutions, students may sleep in libraries or classrooms during examination periods. Under this provision, such students could technically be classified as intruders. Similarly, employees who stage a peaceful protest on company premises due to dissatisfaction with working conditions could fall within the scope of unlawful entry. By failing to account for these practical realities, the provision disregards the limits imposed by the *Constitution* and the *PIE Act* on the long-standing common law principle of absolute ownership.⁵³ Rather than protecting property rights in a measured and reasonable manner, this section risks criminalising ordinary, non-threatening conduct and disproportionately targeting those who are exercising legitimate needs or rights.

Section 5(1) provides for ways in which a notice can be given to a potential “intruder”. It states that a notice may be given –

⁵³ Dhliwayo “Justifying the limitations on the landowner’s right to exclude” 2019 *TSAR* 252; Van der Walt *Property and Constitution* (2012) 29.

- (a) Orally or in writing; or
- (b) By means of a sign posted at or near an ordinary point of access to the premises so that, in daylight and under normal weather conditions, from the approach to the ordinary point of access, the sign is –
 - (i) Clearly visible;
 - (ii) If containing writing, the writing is clearly legible; and
 - (iii) if using graphic representation, the graphic representation is clearly visible.

Section 5(1) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* is fundamentally incompatible with the protections afforded to unlawful occupants under the *PIE Act*. By outlining that a notice may be given orally, in writing, or by a sign at an access point, the provision effectively bypasses the procedural safeguards set out in sections 4, 6, and 7 of the *PIE Act*. Critically, it does not prescribe any minimum notice period, nor does it require judicial oversight, allowing notice to be issued at any stage of an occupation. Such a framework disregards the historical and social complexities of South Africa, including the legacy of forced removals, evictions, and urbanisation under apartheid, which our constitutional framework seeks to root out. In practice, this could result in arbitrary and abrupt notices being served, placing already vulnerable individuals at risk and undermining the careful balance the *Constitution* and the *PIE Act* sought to achieve between property rights and the right of access to housing.

In many cases, occupiers come into and maintain possession of buildings, land or property under a variety of circumstances and for varying lengths of time. It is therefore not uncommon for a person to be born into unlawful occupancy or to spend most of their life under this status. Section 5 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* fails to account for the fact that tenure insecurity is a persistent reality for the majority of poor, primarily black South Africans, who, without state intervention, cannot access secure housing in urban centres that contain essential economic opportunities for low-income households. Moreover, the provisions in section 5(1)(a) allowing notice to be delivered orally could give rise to disputes over whether a notice was properly issued, creating an additional burden of proof in court. This not only exposes occupiers to further vulnerability but also introduces procedural complications that the *Unlawful Entry Bill* does not address.

4.3 Unlawful Entry Bill and Constitutional rights: Freedom of expression, privacy, and the protection of unlawful occupiers

Section 6 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* creates a further offence: the removal, alteration or defacing of a notice in terms of section 5 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*. It states that -

(1) No person, other than a lawful occupier or an authorised person, may remove, alter or deface signs posted as referred to in section 5 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*.

(2) A person who contravenes subsection (1) commits an offence.

Section 6 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* is constitutionally suspect and offends section 16 of the *Constitution*, which guarantees freedom of expression. It is now trite in our law that the right to freedom of expression, as enshrined in the *Constitution*, requires tolerance for the public airing of disagreements and the rejection of efforts to silence unpopular views. This right implicitly recognises the importance, both for a democratic society and for individuals, personally, of the ability to form and express opinions - whether individually or collectively - even where those views are controversial. To criminalise the removal or defacement of a posted sign calling for the immediate eviction of unlawful occupiers from their homes is, in essence, to silence dissent among already marginalised and vulnerable groups in our society. In allowing this, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* clearly creates a new crime of silencing dissent – one that finds no basis in common law or the *Criminal Procedure Act* 51 of 1977, as amended.⁵⁴

As Mokgoro J observed in *Case and Another v Minister of Safety and Security and Others; Curtis v Minister of Safety and Security and Others*,⁵⁵ freedom of expression is one of a “web of mutually supporting rights” in the Constitution.⁵⁶ It is closely linked to freedom of religion, belief and opinion (section 15), the right to dignity (section 10), the right to freedom of association (section 18), the right to vote and to stand for public office (section 19), and the right to assembly (section 17). Taken together, these rights, protect the rights of individuals not only to form and express opinions of any nature, but also to associate with others and collectively promote those opinions.⁵⁷ The effect of the freedom of expression and its related

⁵⁴ *Criminal Procedure Act* 51 of 1977.

⁵⁵ *Case and Another v Minister of Safety and Security and Others; Curtis v Minister of Safety and Security and Others* 1996 (3) SA 617 (CC) (hereafter *Case case*).

⁵⁶ *Case case* para 27.

⁵⁷ *Case case* para 27.

rights is society's tolerance of different views.⁵⁸ Accordingly, unlawful occupiers would be well within their rights to remove posters calling for their summary eviction and replace them with posters declaring "Justice and respect for the poor", or that "We won't move", or that "This is our home." The fact that provisions of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* fall short of these prescripts is a clear indication of its far-reaching and regressive effect, rendering it unsuitable to form part of our statute books.

Section 7 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* creates the duty to inform an "intruder" of an unlawful entry. It provides that -

- (1) As soon as it comes to the attention of the lawful occupier of the premises or an authorised person, they must request the intruder or intruders unlawfully on the premises, to leave the premises immediately.
- (2) If the intruder or intruders does not leave the premises, or the lawful occupier or a person authorised by them are threatened in any manner, the lawful occupier or authorised person must, without delay request assistance from the authorised member of the South African Police Service, as contemplated in section 8(1), informing them of unlawful entry, the address of the premises and the approximate number of intruders.

To the extent that the term "intruder" or "intruders" in the *Unlawful Entry Bill* is used synonymously to denote an "unlawful occupier" or "unlawful occupiers" as defined in the *PIE Act*, this provision is inconsistent with both the *Constitution* and the *PIE Act*. It amounts to a clear reintroduction of the apartheid-era influx control laws, cutting deep into section 14 of the *Constitution*, which guarantees and protects everyone's right to privacy - especially in their home.⁵⁹ Neither the *Constitution* nor the *PIE Act* attach criminal consequences to unlawful occupation. As the Constitutional Court has held in the *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case the purpose and effect of the *PIE Act* is to decriminalise unlawful occupation and to respond with care and compassion to the needs of those who unlawfully occupy their homes.⁶⁰ By effectively re-criminalising unlawful occupation through the use of the term "intruder," the *Unlawful Entry Bill* undermines this Constitutional mandate and revives the punitive, exclusionary logic that the democratic order seeks to abolish.

⁵⁸ *Moyo v Minister of Justice and Constitutional Development; Sonti v Minister of Justice and Correctional Services* 2018 (2) SACR 313 (SCA) para 42.

⁵⁹ *Abolition of Influx Control Act* 68 of 1986, repealed some thirty-four laws controlling the movement of Africans.

⁶⁰ *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case para 12.

4.4 Section 8 of the Unlawful Entry Bill conflicts with section 21 of the Constitution

Section 8 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* deals with the powers of the police. Subsections (1) and (4) respectively grant the authorised member of the South African Police Services the power to remove and arrest “intruders”, if they fail to vacate immediately after being notified, either verbally or in writing. The combined effect of these provisions is to permit what would, in practice, amount to unlawful eviction of persons who may be protected under the *PIE Act*. Section 8(4) re-enforces the regressive tone of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* by making the arrest of the so-called unlawful intruders mandatory. The explicit use of the word “must,” coupled with the reference to housing structures, creates an outrageous and unprecedented offence in South African criminal law – the mere erection of a structure and occupation thereof. This clause undermines not only the *PIE Act* and section 26(3) of the *Constitution* but the very essence of South Africa’s diverse constitutional democracy, which is founded on human dignity, equality, and the rule of law.

As the Constitutional Court observed in the *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case, the *PIE Act* not only repealed PISA - which the *Trespass Act* had been enacted to reinforce – but in a profound sense, inverted it. Through the *PIE Act*, squatting was decriminalised, and evictions were made subject to a set of procedural and substantive safeguards designed to ensure compliance with the dictates of the Bill of Rights.⁶¹ The *Unlawful Entry Bill*’s attempt to criminalise occupation for residential purposes therefore represents the reapplication of PISA by another name and stands in direct violation of section 26(3) of the *Constitution* and the protective framework established by the *PIE Act*. As reaffirmed by the Constitutional Court in the *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case,⁶² the very purpose and effect of the *PIE Act* is to decriminalise unlawful occupation and to require that such situations be addressed with care, compassion, and a respect for human dignity.⁶³

The provisions of section 8(4) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* are, in all likelihood, unconstitutional as they also amount to a deprivation and limitation of both freedom of movement under section 21 of the *Constitution* and the right to freedom and security of the person under section 12(1)(a) of the *Constitution*. Section 8(4) empowers the police to arrest individuals merely for their continued presence on premises, even when such individuals may

⁶¹ *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case para 12.

⁶² *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case para 12.

⁶³ *Port Elizabeth Municipality* case para 37.

be exercising constitutionally recognised rights or protections under the *PIE Act*.

Section 21(3) of the *Constitution* guarantees every citizen the right to reside anywhere in the Republic. This provision is a decisive constitutional shift away from the punitive and exclusionary practices of the apartheid era, which restricted freedom of movement and residence. By enabling the arrest and removal of persons from land or property without judicial oversight, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* resurrects precisely those practices the *Constitution* sought to abolish. It effectively allows the state to prevent people, particularly the poor and landless, from settling or seeking shelter in certain areas - an outcome antithetical to the values of equality, dignity, and freedom on which the South African democratic order is built.

The right to freedom protections of a person under section 12(1)(a) of the *Constitution* is both substantive and procedural.⁶⁴ Substantively, no person may be deprived of liberty arbitrarily or without just cause.⁶⁵ Yet, by criminalising mere presence upon or occupation of land, section 8(4) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* fails to satisfy this requirement and reverts to the apartheid tactics of criminalising unlawful occupation of land. Procedurally, any deprivation of liberty must happen through a fair and just process.⁶⁶ Yet, section 8(4) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* authorises an immediate arrest and removal, without judicial intervention or procedural safeguards, of an unlawful occupier. Such measures mirror the same draconian prescripts of the *Trespass Act* and the PISA, instruments long recognised as incompatible with South Africa's constitutional democracy.

In its current form, section 8(4) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* is in direct conflict with the *Constitution*, the *PIE Act*, and the *Promotion of Administrative Justice Act* 3 of 2000. It represents a legislative regression of criminalisation and coercion, rather than a rights-based approach to housing and land occupation. For these reasons, section 8(4) of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* should be omitted from the final draft of the Bill and any subsequent legislation, as its inclusion alone would render the statute constitutionally indefensible.

⁶⁴ *Malachi v Cape Dance Academy International (Pty) Ltd and Others* 2010 (6) SA 1 (CC) para 25 (hereafter *Malachi case*)

⁶⁵ *Malachi case* para 25.

⁶⁶ *Malachi case* para 25.

In *S v Coetzee and Others*,⁶⁷ where O'Regan J emphasised that the state may not deprive its citizens of liberty for reasons that are not acceptable, nor may it do so in a procedurally unfair manner, even when such deprivation is for legitimate reasons.⁶⁸ Section 8(4) and the *Unlawful Entry Bill* as a whole fall far short of this basic constitutional standard. It fails to respect the substantive rights of unlawful occupiers and makes no provision for procedures through which affected persons may challenge the application of the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, whether by review or internal appeal mechanism processes.

What is even more concerning is that the *Unlawful Entry Bill* expressly calls for “immediate removals” of persons deemed to be intruders. It makes no allowance for meaningful engagement or for obtaining a court order in accordance with the *PIE Act* before an eviction, demolition, arrest, or detention takes place. Simply put, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* authorises arbitrary evictions and summary removals, actions that are fundamentally inconsistent with the Constitution’s commitment to human dignity, equality, and freedom. In bypassing judicial oversight and the procedural safeguards established by the *PIE Act*, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* operates in direct conflict with the rights and protections enshrined in the Bill of Rights.

4.5 Penalties and available defences under the Unlawful Entry Bill

A person facing charges for contravening the *Trespass Act* is not deprived of legal safeguards. To avoid liability under the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, section 9 delineates the possible defences available to a person facing removal from land or property based on accusations of being an intruder. It provides that -

A person may not be convicted of an offence under this Act if the person’s action or inaction, as applicable to the offence, was with —

- (a) the consent of a lawful occupier of the premises or an authorised person;
- (b) other lawful authority; or
- (c) they reasonably believed that they had title to or an interest in the premises that entitled them enter the premises.

Once again, the available defences fail to account for the realities of informality and unlawful occupation, which are deeply entrenched aspects of life in urban settings and beyond. Moreover, section 9 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* does not engage with the *PIE Act* or the extensive jurisprudence

⁶⁷ *S v Coetzee and Others* 1997 (3) SA 527 (CC) (hereafter *S v Coetzee case*).

⁶⁸ *S v Coetzee case* para 159.

of the Constitutional Court,⁶⁹ which recognises the importance of protecting individuals who remain on land or property as unlawful occupiers due to historical colonial and apartheid dispossession, as well as contemporary exclusions from the housing market. As a result, section 9 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* undermines the *Constitution's* transformative objectives. Further, the *Unlawful Entry Bill* provides no guidance on how these defences would be raised procedurally, at what stage they may be invoked, or before which body or forum.

Section 10 of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* deals with penalties and provides that a person who is guilty of an offence under the legislation is, on conviction, liable to a fine or imprisonment for a period not exceeding two years, or to both such fine and imprisonment. This sanction also mirrors that of the *Trespass Act* penalty provision. Despite the *Unlawful Entry Bill* being characterised as a progressive instrument aimed at reforming the legal framework governing land occupation, its punitive provisions reveal it to be a direct reincarnation of its predecessor legislations, the *Trespass Act* and the PISA. By imposing criminal sanctions without adequate procedural safeguards or meaningful defences – as envisaged by section 9 – the *Unlawful Entry Bill* fails to address the realities of informal settlements and unlawful occupation, and risks disproportionately penalising vulnerable individuals. In this way, section 10 not only undermines the transformative objectives of the *Constitution* but also perpetuates the punitive approach that the *PIE Act* explicitly sought to remedy.

As Muller pointed out, the PISA and its complementary legislation, the *Trespass Act*, were grounded in the concept of ownership as a complete and absolute right, granting the state and private landowners the power to evict unlawful occupiers without regard for their personal circumstances or housing needs. This approach relied heavily on the common law remedy of *rei vindication*.⁷⁰ Considering the weight that the *Unlawful Entry Bill* places on private property and ownership, with no reference whatsoever to the relevant provisions of the *Constitution* or the *PIE Act*, it becomes evident

⁶⁹ *Government of the Republic of South Africa and Others v Grootboom and Others* 2001 (1) SA 46; *President of the Republic of South Africa and Another v Modderklip Boerdery (Pty) Ltd* 2005 (5) SA 3 (CC); *Port Elizabeth Municipality v Various Occupiers* 2005 (1) SA 217 (CC); *Occupiers of 51 Olivia Road, Berea Township and 197 Main Street Johannesburg v City of Johannesburg and Others* 2008 (3) SA 208 (CC); *City of Johannesburg Metropolitan Municipality v Blue Moonlight Properties 39 (Pty) Ltd and Another* 2012 (2) SA 104 (CC); and more.

⁷⁰ Muller *The Impact of Section 26 of the Constitution on the Eviction of Squatters in South African Law* 70.

that the *Unlawful Entry Bill* similarly operates on the premise of *rei vindication*, prioritising property rights over the constitutional and statutory protections afforded to vulnerable occupiers.

5 Conclusion

The provisions of the *Unlawful Entry Bill* fail to engage with the *PIE Act* or the protections it extends to poor and vulnerable households who, due to historic dispossession, have been systematically denied formal access to the South African housing market. The *Unlawful Entry Bill* neglects to consider the range of circumstances in which criminalisation of occupation could be used to block access to shelter, housing and tenure security for thousands of people, thereby undermining both the transformative objectives of the Constitution and the broader imperatives of social justice. In the everyday lives of the affected individuals, such provisions risk deepening spatial inequality and perpetuating the cycle of poverty inherited from the previous regime.

Much like the other abolished land laws, the *Trespass Act* was a racially discriminatory instrument that empowered the state and private landowners to enforce evictions and displace black South Africans. In response, the anti-eviction statutory framework of the *PIE Act*, in line with section 26(3) of the *Constitution*, was enacted to prevent such abuses in the democratic South Africa.⁷¹ Accordingly, when an unlawful occupier cannot vacate the occupied property for fear of being rendered homeless, the owner or person in charge must pursue eviction proceedings under the *PIE Act*, following all procedural and substantive safeguards, including provision of alternative accommodation where necessary.⁷² The common law remedy of *rei vindicatio* or the *Trespass Act* cannot govern such matters, rendering the *Unlawful Entry Bill*, which relies on those principles, constitutionally and legally untenable.

In light of the analysis in this article, it is evident that the *Unlawful Entry Bill* fundamentally contradicts the protections afforded by the *PIE Act* and various provisions of the *Constitution*. By criminalising mere occupation, authorising immediate removals without judicial oversight, and failing to provide meaningful procedural safeguards or guidance for defences. The *Unlawful Entry Bill* undermines, amongst others, the rights to adequate housing, freedom of movement, and security of the person. Section 8(1) of

⁷¹ Van Der Walt *Constitutional Property Law* 521.

⁷² Section 4(1) of the *PIE Act*.

the *Constitution* provides that the Bill of Rights applies to all laws and binds the legislature, the executive, the judiciary and all organs of state.

Accordingly, all laws must be capable of an interpretation that promotes the spirit, purport and objects of the Bill of Rights to pass constitutional muster. Where legislation limits rights, such limitation must be justifiable in an open and democratic society as contemplated in section 36 of the *Constitution*.⁷³ The *Unlawful Entry Bill*, in its current form, fails to meet these constitutional standards and should be comprehensively redrafted to align with the *PIE Act*, the transformative mandate of the *Constitution*, and the protection of vulnerable persons.

⁷³ *NUMSA & Others v Bader Bop (Pty) Limited & Another* 2003 (3) SA 513 (CC) para 37.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Literature

Dhliwayo “Justifying the limitations on the landowner’s right to exclude” 2019 *TSAR*

Dhliwayo P “Justifying the limitations on the landowner’s right to exclude” 2019 *TSAR* 252-284

Du Plessis 2005 *SALJ*

Du Plessis LM “The (Re)-systemization of the Canons and Aids to Statutory Interpretation’ (2005) 112 *SALJ* 591-613

Dugard “International Law and the South African Constitution” 1997 *EJIL*

Dugard J “International Law and the South African Constitution” 1997 *EJIL* 77-92

Harrison 1992 *African Insight*

Harrison P “The Policies and Politics of Informal Settlement in South Africa: A Historical Perspective” 1992 *African Insight* 14-22

Kloppers and Pienaar 2014 *PELJ*

Kloppers HJ and Pienaar GJ “The Historical Context of Land Reform in South Africa and early policies” 2014 *PELJ* 677-706

Muller *The Impact of Section 26 of the Constitution on the Eviction of Squatters in South African Law*

Muller G *The Impact of Section 26 of the Constitution on the Eviction of Squatters in South African Law* (LLD thesis, Stellenbosch University 2011)

Nieftagodien *The Soweto Uprising*

Nieftagodien N *The Soweto Uprising* (Jacana Media 2014)

Snyman *Criminal Law*

Snyman C *Criminal Law* 5th ed (Lexis Nexis 2008)

Strauss 2019 *Fundamina*

Strauss M “A Historical Exposition of Spatial Injustice and Segregated Urban Settlement in South Africa” 2019 *Fundamina* 135-168

Van der Walt *Constitutional Property Law*

Van der Walt AJ *Constitutional Property Law* 3rd ed (Juta 2011)

Walker and Cousins *Land Divided, Land Restored*

Walker C and Cousins B *Land Divided, Land Restored* (Jacana Media 2014)

Wilson, Dugard and Clark 2015 *SAJHR*

Wilson S, Dugard J and Clark M "Conflict Management in an era of Urbanisation: Twenty Years of Housing Rights in the Constitutional Court" 2015 *SAJHR* 472-503

Case Law

Case and Another v Minister of Safety and Security and Others; Curtis v Minister of Safety and Security and Others 1996 (3) SA 617 (CC)

City of Johannesburg Metropolitan Municipality v Blue Moonlight Properties 39 (Pty) Ltd and Another 2012 (2) SA 104 (CC)

City of Johannesburg v Changing Tides 74 (Pty) Ltd and Others 2012 (6) SA 294 (SCA)

Department of Land Affairs v Goedgelegen Tropical Fruits (Pty) Ltd 2007 (6) SA 199 (CC)

Government of the Republic of South Africa and Others v Grootboom and Others 2001 (1) SA 46 (CC)

Machele and Others v Mailula and Others 2010 (2) SA 257 (CC)

Malachi v Cape Dance Academy International (Pty) Ltd and Others 2010 (6) SA 1 (CC)

Moyo v Minister of Justice and Constitutional Development; Sonti v Minister of Justice and Correctional Services 2018 (2) SACR 313 (SCA)

Ndlovu v Ngcobo; Bekker and Another v Jika 2003 (1) SA 113 (SCA)

NUMSA & Others v Bader Bop (Pty) Limited & Another 2003 (3) SA 513 (CC)

Occupiers of 51 Olivia Road, Berea Township and 197 Main Street Johannesburg v City of Johannesburg and Others 2008 (3) SA 208 (CC)

Occupiers of Skurweplaas 353 JR v PPC Aggregate Quarries (Pty) Ltd and Others 2012 (4) BCLR 382 (CC)

Port Elizabeth Municipality v Various Occupiers 2005 (1) SA 217 (CC)

President of the Republic of South Africa and Another v Modderklip Boerdery (Pty) Ltd 2005 (5) SA 3 (CC)

R v Maduma 1959 (4) SA 204 (N)

R v Mgwali 1961 (1) SA 51 (E)

S v Coetzee and Others 1997 (3) SA 527 (CC)

S v Ziki 1965 (4) SA 14 (E)

Legislation

Abolition of Influx Control Act 68 of 1986

Abolition of Racially Based Land Measures Act 108 of 1991

Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996

Criminal Law Amendment Act 59 of 1983

Criminal Procedure Act 51 of 1977.

Extension of Security of Tenure Act 62 of 1997

Native Land Act 27 of 1913

Prevention of Illegal Evictions from and Unlawful Occupation of Land Act 19 of 1998

Prevention of Illegal Squatting Act 52 of 1951

Promotion of Administrative Justice Act 3 of 2000

Trespass Act 6 of 1959

Unlawful Entering on Premises Bill, 2022

South African government publications

Gen Not 46705 in GG 1219 of 12 August 2022.

Internet sources

Department of Justice and Constitutional Development
https://www.justice.gov.za/m_statements/2022/20220816-UnlawfulEntry-Bill.html accessed on 5 October 2025.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EJIL	European Journal of International Law
PER / PELJ	Potchefstroom Elektroniese Regstydskrif / Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal
SAJHR	South African Journal on Human Rights
SALJ	South African Law Journal
TSAR	Tydskrif van die Suid-Afrikaanse Reg / Journal of South African Law